

D1.2: Data Management Plan

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X	PU: Public
	PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
	RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
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Abbreviations and Acronyms

DMP	Data Management Plan
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable
RDA	Research Data Alliance
WG	Working Group

A Data Management Plan created using DMPTuuli (www.dmptuuli.fi)

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RDA TIGER - Data management plan (after 6 months)

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Executive Summary

This deliverable lists the types of the data produced in the RDA TIGER project via the RDA TIGER personnel. The data storage and management solutions, and their role in the data lifetime are discussed. The DMP also includes information on the project and partner allocation of resources, data security, ethics and exploitation.

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1. Data Summary

The project collects the following kinds of data (the work package (WP) most concerned with the data type are noted in parentheses).

- I. **Internal project documents (all WPs).** These documents contain working documents on service descriptions, milestones, deliverables and other similar internal documents and contracts. These are created in the project lifetime by the project partners, and are usually normal office documents (text documents, spreadsheets, etc.), of small size. This data has limited interest outside of the consortium, and in the long term.
- II. **External project documentation (Deliverables, other reports, dissemination material) (all WPs).** These documents are official outputs of the project, including service descriptions, quality indicators, and service processes, as well as project publications and dissemination materials. These documents are all public and intended for re-use later, and licenced with an open licence allowing wide re-use. The size of this data is limited (below 1Gb), and typically small PDF documents. The data will be utilised by RDA in the future, as well as other organisations wanting to create similar services for supporting group work globally.
- III. **Contact lists (WP1 and WP2).** These are personal contact information on the WG members, RDA TIGER stakeholders, and project personnel and involved parties. This data is in different structured formats (e.g., spreadsheets), and of small size. There is no intention of using this data after the project ends, and this data will be permanently deleted.
- IV. **Data and documents regarding applications (WP1 and WP6).** The contact information is collected via RDA WG registration processes, as well as internally in the project. The WG membership information is used by the RDA to target members with specified information (which they have actively opted in when registering and can cancel at any moment). Approved applications are made public and archived properly in the RDA website. Non-successful applications will be deleted after decision. There is no other intended re-use of this data, and remaining data will be deleted after the review unless specifically asked by the applicant (e.g. for re-submission purposes).
- V. **Open science landscape data (WP3).** This data comprises information on open science initiatives, RDA groups, outputs, and similar complex objects, and their respective connections. This data is principally collected in structured formats - initially spreadsheets, but later reformatted during the project time to more organized heterogenous graph database. The data content is information on projects, initiatives, and outputs, as well as internet links. The dataset is intended to be re-usable after the project in other contexts.
- VI. **Service quality indicators and feedback (WP6).** The service feedback data are datasets collected from targets, providers, customers, and beneficiaries of the RDA TIGER services. They can sometimes contain personal information (if the reviewer has left such information for contacting them), but in most cases this information is removed after resulting communication. Some of the quality indicator information is restructured for anonymity or analysis. The indicators are both numeric and qualitative, usually stored in spreadsheets and text documents. The quality information is intended to be re-used in abridged form after the project end to improve the service usability.

- VII. **Working Group documents and outputs (WP5).** These are documents produced by the supported Working Groups themselves with significant facilitation or other support help by the RDA TIGER personnel (i.e. the outputs have significant intellectual commitment from the RDA TIGER). The documents are open to the public by the rules of the Research Data Alliance. The outputs are intended to be found and re-used as much as possible, although intermediate results (e.g., draft versions) rarely are.

2. FAIR DATA

The data created in the RDA TIGER are stored and managed in a set of different data service platforms. The following table summarises the main usage of these systems per data type.

*Table 1 Data management solutions used in the RDA TIGER per data type. "Working" refers to document location during the project-time activities (e.g., drafts, online shared documents being edited, etc.), and "long term" refers to a solution intended for long time data management (including after-project storage). Terms in parenthesis indicate secondary or temporary use. *) only for successful applications and their relevant associated information, **) only connectivity (i.e., metadata and linkages) are stored in this facility, not the actual data.*

Data no	Type	Google folders	RDA Website	Commission	Zenodo	B2DROP	Sharepoint	Maintenance facility
I	Internal documents	Working					Long term	
II	External documents	Working	Long term	Long term	Long term			Long term **
III	Contact lists	(working)					Working	
IV	Applications		Long term*			Working		
V	Landscape data	(working)						Working, long term
VI	Quality data	Working					(working)	
VII	WG data		working, long term		(long term)			Long term **

Below, we discuss the different data management tools used, and adhere to the FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability) principles.

2.1 Google folder tree

Corresponding data types: I, II, (III), (V), VI

Google-operated office suite (drive.google.com) and shared documents. For the documents and information needed for mostly internal purposes, the main findability issue is to make sure they are shareable and secure in the internal storage systems of the project. For non-critical or documents having no specific security requirements, a shared Google folder system is used, where the documents are arranged according to the WP. This folder tree is maintained by WP1.

FAIR implications: Findability via folder structure by project consortium members only. Accessibility: For project internal use, access limited to WP participants. Interoperability: Limited internal

metadata included in most documents for internal use, use of standard templates for critical information. Necessary metadata for internal use is included in the files as much as is reasonable. Re-usability: Not intended for re-use after the project.

2.2. RDA website

Corresponding data types: II, IV, VII

Website platform (rd-alliance.org), with a rich document repository and wide range of information, particularly for the Working Group documents. The platform is being updated (partly via contribution via RDA TIGER service purchase) and will act as the main virtual collaboration platform for WG work (type VII). The document platform also includes additional documentation of RDA (types II and partially IV) and is commonly seen as the primary platform for the community to search for RDA documents. The platform has long term sustainability, and it has a regular back-up schedule.

FAIR implications: Findability via tagging and persistent (i.e. non-changing in technology migration) URLs (also linked in many DOIs). Accessibility: Generally open access, some documents (mostly working documents) only for the WG members. Interoperability: Limited internal metadata included in most documents, use of standard templates for critical information. Necessary metadata for internal use is included in the files as much as is reasonable. Re-usability: Document platform is available for re-use, although lack of specific metadata or documentation can limit the usability of some outputs. This should be considered in WP4 actions for output documentation.

2.3. Commission services

Corresponding data types: II

The European Commission operates their own document repository for project outputs, particularly for the project deliverables. In practice, all RDA TIGER deliverables which are public are de-facto published in the CORDIS database (cordis.europa.eu) for public use, and the platform acts as a permanent repository of these documents.

FAIR implications: Findability via tagging and permanent URLs, although by experience small number of direct searchers are done in these services. Accessibility: Openly accessible with no registration. Interoperability: Limited internal metadata included in most documents, use of standard templates for critical information. Necessary metadata for internal use is included in the files as much as is reasonable. Re-usability: Depending on document.

2.4. Zenodo

Corresponding data types: II, VII

Zenodo platform (zenodo.org) offers a long-term document and data repository for general datasets. Operated by CERN, it has a service promise for sustained long term stability. The RDA TIGER public documents are co-hosted in the Zenodo, and are included in the RDA and RDA TIGER communities for easier access. The metadata for these records is standardised for the outputs uploaded by the RDA TIGER.

FAIR implications: Findability via metadata, DOIs and multiple services harvesting the Zenodo APIs. Accessibility: Openly accessible with no registration. Interoperability: Limited internal metadata included in most documents, use of standard templates for critical information. Necessary metadata for internal use is included in the files as much as is reasonable. Re-usability: Depending on document.

2.5. B2DROP

Corresponding data types: IV

B2DROP platform (b2drop.eudat.eu) offers a medium-term (non-permanent, but several years) document and data repository for datasets. The EUDAT operates these servers in Europe, and the access can be easily controlled for multiple kinds of users per document or per folder basis. B2DROP uses B2ACCESS service offering a wide range of federated identity providers in addition to specific B2DROP user identities. The B2DROP is used in the RDA TIGER only to facilitate the RDA TIGER application management, as the platform allows specified access to only relevant parties to the applications (e.g., Selection board can read the applications, reviewers can only access the applications they review, and the review results are only visible to selection board members). The B2DROP is not intended for long-term storage, although the system has historically been operated for a relatively long time. RDA TIGER application information (particularly for non-successful applications) will be immediately deleted after the documents are no longer needed. The successful application data is moved to the RDA web platform (2.1 above) for public access.

FAIR implications: Findability via direct links provided on need-to-access basis by WP6. Accessibility: Access control allowing access for strictly specified personnel. Interoperability: Applications have internal metadata. Re-usability: not intended for re-use.

2.6. SHAREPOINT

Corresponding data types: I, III, (VI)

Internal virtual platform of the RDA Association (operated by RDA Foundation) and provided by the Microsoft services. Access to this platform is more secured and limited than for the Google services (2.1. above). The platform has the benefit of business-level backup services (paid by RDA Association contract). This service is used in RDA TIGER for longer term storage and secondary saving location for some of the documents not intended for public access, particularly raw service feedback data and contact lists which need to be secured due to GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) concerns.

FAIR implications: Findability via internal folder system and document naming. Accessibility: Only for strictly specified personnel. Interoperability: Applications have internal metadata. Re-usability: only internal use.

2.7. RDA Maintenance facility

Corresponding data types: II, V, VII

Internally developed long-term tagging and findability allowing database, which stores key metadata (tags) of RDA WGs (Working Group), WG outputs and WP3 created Open Science landscape resources. Notably, the facility is not intended as a data repository, but instead a virtual metadata and connectivity tool (graph database), which will enable the long-term findability and connectivity (re-use) of the documents involved. This service is described in more detail in the deliverable D4.1¹.

FAIR implications: The RDA Maintenance facility, particularly as it is connected to the RDA (upgraded) website, will provide additional findability of the digital records involved in the facility. The Maintenance facility will provide additional accessibility and interoperability of due to additional metadata involved in the documented data systems. Reusability will be significantly improved due to tagging with topic-related keywords of interest to the community, for example the GORC vocabulary (as it is being developed in the RDA GORC WG).

3. Allocation of resources

The project involves internal resources for data management, particularly in the WP1, WP4, and WP6. The resources include personnel resources for the management activities, as well as development of Maintenance facility connectivity in WP4. Additionally, the project includes resources for concrete management actions:

- Partial funding of RDA Website development task to make sure the website is usable for the RDA TIGER support services. This contribution is marked as direct purchase of goods and is handled via contract with RDA Foundation.
- WP1 includes direct costs to pay for partial use (for RDA Association personnel) of the SharePoint service platform.

The usage of Zenodo, B2DROP and Commission services are currently free at the point-of-use.

4. Data security

The data produced in the RDA TIGER project has modest data security needs. Documents under preparation (Type I) need only to be shared to the relevant participants, but in general this can be reached with a modest security approach (e.g., via shared public link in emails). More security-

¹ 10.5281/zenodo.8058923

oriented developments can be controlled by more stringent access, with (increasing level of security):

- 1) Openly shared Google documents in edit-mode
- 2) Openly shared Google documents in comment/suggest mode
- 3) Specific-accounts-only - accessible Google documents
- 4) SharePoint documents (only accessible with SharePoint accounts internal to RDA Association)
- 5) B2DROP documents (only accessible to specific persons controlled by WP6)

The RDA TIGER personnel are instructed on the correct security level used for different documents based on their need.

The Google document folders are regularly backed-up to secure servers in SharePoint by WP1, and WP4 creates back-ups of the RDA Maintenance facility in the DANS/KNAW Vault long-term preservation facility.

6. Ethics

The RDA TIGER considers the ethical aspects of the recorded data.

- Many datasets of the RDA TIGER, particularly connected to the WG work, will include some level of personal information, particularly on the membership of the WG members. Although the membership in the RDA groups is public knowledge due to the RDA membership policies, this information is considered protected by the GDPR, and the retention of such information is controlled by WP1. The data protection statements and clear documentation on the usage of the data is provided to the WG members as per normal RDA policy. Data controller for the RDA Website published data is RDA Secretariat (based in the UK) but will follow the GDPR requirements.
- To the extent to which RDA members are also authors of formal RDA outputs, such information will be included in bibliographic metadata in Zenodo and in the RDA Maintenance Facility, and are generally considered to be publicly available for purposes of findability and citation.
- Other data with more important ethical concerns, such as information on RDA TIGER applications, and particularly the reviewers' identity and review scores are controlled by WP6. This information will be destroyed immediately after the need for use of the information passes.

7. Other issues

7.1. Exploitation of the RDA TIGER and WG outputs

Although the actual exploitation plan of RDA TIGER is presented in the D4.2, there is also a need to consider the result exploitation from the perspective of the datasets produced. The RDA TIGER plans to concentrate the exploitation of the data products to the following key channels:

- 1) Service descriptions of the RDA TIGER services, including their user feedback and quality control aspects (without any personal data). These are intended to have long term storage in the RDA website, with additional storage in the Zenodo repository. However, it is also important to note, that these outputs are then widely distributed and communicated to the RDA regional nodes and other RDA member organisations. They are also included in the RDA maintenance facility.
- 2) The exploitation and user-based enrichment of the RDA Landscape data in the RDA Maintenance facility, and connecting the database with other landscape-creating studies, such as EOSC FOCUS, and GORC.

The ensuring exploitation of these outputs is an additional long term target of the data management activities of the project.

